

LANGUAGE AND CULTURE IN ENGLISH CLASSROOMS: WAYS OF ADDRESSING, IDIOMS

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Abstract: This article highlights the ways students greet and express politeness in different cultures. Also, communication patterns in Japanese and English were analyzed.

Key words: culture, greeting, Japanese language, English language, politeness, forms of address, linguistic tool.

Cultural Awareness is the foundation of communication and it involves the capability of standing back from ourselves and getting apprehensive of our artistic values, beliefs and comprehensions. Why do we do effects in that way? How do we see the world? Why do we reply in that particular way?

Cultural mindfulness becomes central when we've to interact with people from other societies. People see, interpret and estimate effects in a different way. What's considered an applicable geste in one culture is constantly unhappy in another one, misconstructions arise when I use my meanings to make sense of your reality.

As an Italian it's nearly automatic to perceive US Americans as people who always work, talk about business over lunch and drink their coffee running in the road

general, the form of the alternate person plural pronoun is addressed to one Hearer as a means of indicating formality and/ or politeness, and is determined by social distance or status differences between the interactants in the hassle[2]. Another thing to mention then's that the pronoun V itself doesn't need to appear in the judgment, because in Greek the inflectional system of the verb indicates person and number and makes particular pronouns spare.

Eventually, we can say that in Greek formalism, social distance and politeness can be expressed through the polite plural. Polite plurals can only be used in direct address and are limited to the use of a alternate plural verb for a single addressee[3].

The speaker's correct choice of pronouns and verb figures when addressing a Listener determines the status of the meeting. Avoidance of this verbal tool in further anticipated situations may lead to a communication breakdown or convey certain ideas and passions from the Speaker towards the Listener and/ or their relationship.

Operation forms in Greek

In addition to the T/ V pronominal system, Greek includes a variety of address options, listed then.

Title(T)(kirie, kiria, despinis)

First Name(FN)

Title Name(TFN)

Surname(LN)

Title Surname(TLN)

Title Position Title

Multiple Naming (MN)

Naming (NN)

The form TFN, absent in English, is an intermediate possibility in Greek, helping to bridge the gap between formality and closeness. Also, this particular construction is presumably the most used in everyday meetings[4]. The choice of number is determined by the form of the address. The listener's FN is always followed by the alternate singular, while the plural is used with T and T LN. The construction T FN can be either singular or plural. In addition to the common titles Mr.(kirios), Mrs.(kiria) and Miss(espinis), there are some words that can be used as impersonal and longer forms of address. These forms include professions or position (PT) and respect. For illustration, the forms of professional titles are dikigore (nonfictional meaning of dikigoros" counsel"), kadiyita(kadigitis" professor"), gatre (gatros" croaker"), etc. exemplifications of honorifics are sevazmiotatat and aksiotime(vocative of sevazmiotatos" most honorable" and axiothymos" good of respect"). Honorifics noway antecede other titles, but a Greek speaker might say, for illustration, kirie dikasta(a compression of kirios dikastis" joe judge") or kirie dimarru(joe kirios dimaros" joe mayor"etc.[5].

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